

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Solutions of the final sorting of End-of-Life Vehicle Shredder Light Fraction.

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Executive Summary

This document describes the actions performed during the execution of *subtask 5.3.2. Solutions of the final sorting of End-of-Life Vehicle Shredder Light Fraction.*

Corresponding to the deliverable 5.4., the document defines the different steps, trials and techniques we have developed to obtain a final product or material ready to use in other applications. The interaction to other companies and the difficulties we have found.

Through the document we will find the different separation technologies used to achieve the common objective, a high-value raw material.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the document and pursue

The objective of the document is to gather the information about all different tasks developed.

End-of-life vehicles (ELV) plastics recycling must play a key role to comply with recycling targets set by the ELV Directive. The **minimum amount of ELV plastics to be recycled by 2020 to meet the EU targets is estimated at 30%, well above 17% in 2012.**

End-of-life vehicles generate between 6 and 8 million tonnes of waste every year in the European Union. **ELVs are a complex mixture of materials that can cause major environmental and health problems if not properly managed.** Moreover, the improvement of ELV dismantling and recycling is essential to boost a circular economy and enhance resource efficiency.

EU legislation promoting the proper management of ELVs has been in force since 2000. The ELV Directive (European Commission, 2000) lays down measures aimed at the prevention of waste from vehicles, as well as measures to promote the reusability, recyclability and recoverability of ELVs and their components; e.g., by pushing producers to limit the use of hazardous substances in new vehicles and to incorporate recycled materials. It also sets out ambitious quantified targets for reuse, recycling and recovery of ELVs and their components to reduce waste disposal.

The aim of the document is to define and apply separation technologies to achieve high-value raw material. From AIMPLAS we are searching an innovative Post Shredder Technology to be implemented to achieve a high sorting separation for the ELV plastic fraction.

Approximately 75% of ELV weight consists of metals (ferrous and non-ferrous) which are easily recycled, but there is still 10% that needs to be recycled additionally to ensure the achievement of the 85% target established as of 2015. **Other materials present in ELVs –such as plastics (9-12wt%), rubber (3 wt%), glass (3 wt%) and textiles (2 wt%)– have a high potential to contribute to the recycling target, but they have played a very**

limited role to date. In the next figure we could see the density ranges of automotive plastic materials.

Figure 1. Density ranges of automotive plastic materials. Source: ICARRE 95

Furthermore, we are interested to obtain a high purity of textile fibres and plastics fraction taking away any potential contaminant elements: dust, dirtiness, light materials and metallic content.

After performing a necessary number of treatments and the analysis of the products obtained defines the optimal one, high value materials will probably be supplied for further recycling processes.

1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

The related WPs with the current deliverable are WP2: Design framework for the three circular products sector and WP3: Material development/conditioning for circular products.

It is very useful to the proper development of the project to have a knowledge in both ways knowing what is done in WP2 to design more circular and ecological products. One of the objectives of the project is to gather the knowledge and the experience about the actual

designs to in a future stage try to re-design the products in an ecofriendly way which means more recyclable and re-manufacturable.

Furthermore, the interaction with WP2 is very important to design a circular validation and a circular application by sharing information between all partners, helping so, all the value chain to improve.

Referred to WP3, these two sections are highly connected in terms of how to evaluate and allow the recycling process to be economically positive as well as recover valuable components to increase the value market products.

It would be very important to being informed between these two actions if we want to achieve a great and positive result to the whole project.

2. Actions

2.1. Analysis of the necessities of fibre and plastics quality.

The scope of this action is the acquisition of a wide range Knowledge of the most valued plastics, and type of fibres that can be obtained from ELV, based on the knowledge of the three partners and vehicles manufacturers information.

In this section we will study the actual consumption and trends of fibres, prioritising the most valued ones as well as to the recycled plastics in the actual market.

Furthermore, we will get the knowledge of the most frequent parts to extract from vehicles, in order to define where to focus the main efforts and to finally select the best ELV shredder light fraction from this fragmentation facilities, defining their value and future benefits for the project.

The market trend on fibers consumption is largely dominated by synthetic fibers respect to other natural fibers (Figure 2). Polyester, nylon and acrylic are the most popularly used synthetic fibers. In this segment, polyester consumption dominates the scenario by 77%, followed by nylon with 12.9 %, acrylic with 8.6% and other fibers making 1.5%. All fiber types succeeded to expand with the exception

of acrylic fibers (-4%) and polyamide enjoyed most dynamics by rising 9% while large-scale polyester just advanced 1%.

Polyester can also be blended with other fibers effectively to enhance the look and durability of the fabric. It is blended with cotton for getting stain and wrinkle resistance. Blending with wool gives the fabric wrinkle resistance and retention of shape during any type of weather conditions. Mixing with rayon gives resilient and durable abilities to the fabric. Combination of polyester with nylon gives strength and abrasion resistance to the clothes.

The global synthetic fiber market is expected to reach USD 88.5 billion by 2025, according to a new report by Grand View Research, Inc. The superior chemical, physical and mechanical properties of synthetic fibers are further expected to propel the demand over the forecast period.

In terms of revenue, polyester was the largest segment in 2016 and the trend is anticipated to continue at a growth rate of 6.3% over the forecast period. The useful chemical properties such as resistance to moisture, chemical and abrasion are expected to boost the demand among the consumers over the forecast period. Polyester has been extensively used in clothing applications on account durability, wrinkle and stain resistance. The polyester when mixed with other synthetic fibers improves the surface appearance as it imparts high luster.

Synthetic fiber is used in various applications, such as clothing, home furnishing, automotive, and filtration, as it imparts useful functional properties including heat and moisture resistance. The increasing spending capability of customers toward purchasing attractive clothing is expected to trigger the demand for various types of synthetic fibers. These factors together are anticipated to boost the demand over the forecast period.

The demand for synthetic fiber will further be driven by the growth in clothing in developed economies including the U.S., Germany, the UK, and France. In particular, companies in synthetic fiber business are also undergoing expansion on account of increased demand from developed economies.

Over the past years, global cotton consumption has fallen short of 15 million bales due to soaring prices. Reduced cotton production and higher prices led to a decline in the global cotton consumption.

Increased prices in cotton will result in the textile mills looking for cheaper options. This will make polyester a good cotton substitute.

Statista 2018

Figure 2 - Distribution of fiber consumption worldwide in 2017 by type of fiber.

Fiber Availability

Natural fibers require a long time to restock the production although it is renewable sources, they can't fulfill the market request in terms of continuous production. One major factor that affects how much the industry may invest in utilizing natural fibers is its availability. This is mainly due to the fact that this property will directly affect the continuity of the production and the price of both raw material and the final product. The annual production of raw natural fibers of plant origins varies from year to year and from type to type.

However, organic fibers have numerous advantages over the conventional synthetic cotton such as no use of pesticides or chemicals that saves the farmers as well as surroundings from chronic diseases, less resource consumption, more revenues for farmers, improved water utilization, and increased biodiversity. Owing to these qualities of the product, demand for organic fibers are expected to increase in the near future hence driving the industry growth.

Cost Production

Manufacturer needs a high cost in terms of production for natural fiber. Several stages are required like harvesting and cleaning before the stock can be obtained to convert into textile products. This makes the natural base products need to be sold at a high price compare with the synthetic ones oil based. Furthermore, considering the actual worldwide economy trend, energy experts forecast that oil prices will settle down somewhat in 2018, as tight supplies ease a bit, which will limit the ability of fiber producers to further increase of their production prices.

However, while for synthetic because it is obtainable from industrial processes, it's possible to save money and time reducing also the production costs of the textile products. Furthermore, their unlimited availability by stock makes the cost production much cheaper than natural fibers.

Life-Expectancy

As well-known, natural fiber is originated from the natural sources which make it have the ability to degrade on naturally or with chemically helps. This would make the life expectancy of natural to be shorter than synthetic. As it is degraded naturally, natural fiber will contribute less to environment's pollution. Nevertheless, Synthetic requires chemically help to degrade the materials which will contribute to environment pollution because of the chemical treatment usage. This will make natural fiber trends to be green-earth in terms of life expectancy and environment's pollution.

<i>Properties/Type of fiber</i>	<i>Natural fiber</i>	<i>Synthetic fiber</i>
Availability	Limited	Unlimited
Homogeneity	Low	High
Cost production	High	Low
Life expectancy	Short-medium	Long
Chemical treatments	Less	High

Table 1 - General comparison between natural and synthetic fibers.

In terms of recycled plastic market, the European plastics industry includes plastics raw materials producers, plastics converters, plastic recyclers and plastics machinery manufactures. These activities cause, for instance, a direct benefit to the market as around 1.5 million of jobs are created due to the plastic industry.

Considering the market data, the European production of plastics includes (thermoplastics and polyurethanes) and other polymers (thermosets, adhesives, coatings and sealants). In Europe, it is estimated around 60 million of tonnes in 2016. The six larger European countries (Germany, Italy, France, Spain, United Kingdom and Poland) and the Benelux cover almost the 80% of the European demand, which means approximately 49.9 million of tonnes.

This number of plastics produced have a European distribution in the main market sectors as follows.

Figure 3- Plastics converter demand main market sectors. Source: PlasticsEurope

Observing the percentage, the two majority markets focused in plastics are packaging (39.9%) and building and construction (19.7%).

Going through this quantity of data but sorting by polymer types, the major quantity of the materials are the polyolefins (PP and PE).

Figure 4- European plastics converter demand by polymer types. Source: PlasticsEurope

To go further, next chart informs us about the European plastics converter demand by segments and polymers types. Considering former graphs we have seen, we could conclude that crossing values the highest obtained are packaging business and polymer LDPE.

As an important point and regarding Ecobulk project the top three sectors with a major percentage of demand are Packaging, Building and Construction and Automotive area.

Figure 5- European plastics converter demand by segments and polymer types. Source: PlasticsEurope

Focusing on automotive sector and the shredder facilities, we observed that the most frequent parts to extract from internal car parts are the following plastics and fibres (PP, PA, ABS, PE and PVC).

We transform these three streams in a useful sample to be analysed in AIMPLAS, so the result was a 3 different points of production line in the partner facilities. The products obtained were sorted by granulometry and type of density.

Component	Types of plastic	Weight in average car (kg)
Bumper	PP, ABS, PC/PBT	10
Seating	PU, PP, PVC, ABS, PA	13
Dashboard	PP, ABS, SMA, PPE, PC	7
Fuel system	HDPE, POM, PA, PP, PBT	6
Body (incl. panels)	PP, PPE, UP	6
Under-bonnet components	PA, PP, PBT	9
Interior trim	PP, ABS, PET, POM, PVC	20
Electrical components	PP, PE, PBT, PA, PVC	7
Exterior trim	ABS, PA, PBT, POM, ASA, PP	4
Lighting	PC, PBT, ABS, PMMA, UP	5
Upholstery	PVC, PU, PP, PE	8
Liquid containers	PP, PE, PA	1

Table 2 –Most common plastic types and components in ELVs. Source: JRC

Regarding the previously work and having an extended knowledge about the best fractions to be treated as well as to include them in the project, we finally selected three streams in total.

First one is related to the front part of the vehicles. It is a rigid plastic usually made of Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), Polypropylene (PP) or a mix of both materials. It is an easy or frequent part to remove from cars and a valuable product in terms of its homogeneity.

Second material chosen is a foamed material which correspond to internal car parts. It is made of Polyurethane (PU) and from our experience and concerning mechanical and physical properties a good product to find a final application during the project.

Third material selected and, in the frame to analyse, correspond to the last stream recovered from the fragmentation facilities. The result is a 3mm granulometry mix composed of different materials (PVC, copper, textile fibres, small pieces of ABS). This stream is the hardest one to analyse trough the project, so next steps of the deliverable will be focused on it.

2.2 Overview of the most common Post Shredder Technologies.

The scope of this action is to check the existing technologies to use recycled plastics and fibres as raw material, as well as analyse the advantages and disadvantages of each equipment.

It is important to contemplate the condition required for the machinery able to process the product obtained as a raw material.

Usually, the ELV plastics recycling process will involve the following steps:

1. **Reception of vehicles**, temporary storage, decontamination and dismantling of currently reusable or recoverable components (like second-hand spares or tyres). These are previous process steps that are already conducted at authorised treatment facilities (ATF).
2. **Dismantling** of target plastic components from vehicles (PP bumpers and HDPE deposits). It will be conducted by workers at the ATFs using standardised methods adapted from ICARRE 95, including manual dismantling assisted with electric and non-electric tools as well as destructive methods.
3. **Sorting** of different plastics components by plastic type. Workers at the ATFs will classify and separate bumpers and deposits in different containers, since they are made of different plastics materials (PP and HDPE) that must be recycled separately to reach good technical properties (not melted and reprocessed together in downstream recycling processes).
4. **Size reduction** of plastic components. It will be conducted at ATFs through a two-step process encompassing shredding and grinding of plastic components into regrinds.
5. **Washing** of plastic regrinds to remove pollutants and unwanted materials. A washing unit will be used to remove contaminants like dust or remaining fuel in deposits. In addition, this unit will be used to remove unwanted materials like metals or (more dense) technical plastics by means of sink-float separation.
6. **Compounding** of recycled plastics. An extrusion process will be used at the recycler/compounder facilities to reprocess the plastic regrinds into recycled plastic pellets, which can also include a part of virgin polymers, additives and/or fillers.

Figure 6- Current ELV Management model

Currently there are a lot of different types of technologies prepared to have an accurate selection of some materials. Generally, all the equipment's are suitable to separate different materials, to use a specific one depends on the income of the facility. It is able on the market machinery for all kinds of materials. However, focusing of post shredding treatments, the main technologies available are as follows.

1- Separation by optical NIR: This technology is continuously growing and because of that we consider it is a key fact to investigate about it. NIR is an optical sorting technology that enables plastic and plastic wastes to be separated by polymer type. NIR technology allows the production of high-quality materials which can substitute virgin polymers in the manufacture of new items. The effective and reliable NIR sorting operations are fundamental to producing high purity segregated polymer streams and achieving maximum market value for products.

The working process is by reading the polymer reflection, the infrared light read the plastic product and depending of what is interesting to sort the software is programmed. The selected fraction is usually ejecting by an air valve and the other materials are going to other container falling by gravity. Next pictures give us a detailed description.

Figure 7- NIR separation process

2-Densimetric tables: Densimetric separation tables are successfully used separating a wide number of products with an application in many industrial sectors. Densimetric separation with air can be used with up to 80 mm fractions and it normally requires for previously classified materials through a screening in granulometric strips, whose size relationship will be bigger or smaller according to the features (real density, shapes, etc.) of the products to be separated.

Figure 8- Densimetric table separation process

The densimetric table is a fluid bed: a vibrant soil with injected air creates a bed of particles that, by density, moves towards one or another side depending on the weight. This allows that material of different densities and granulometries could be separated

3- Pneumatic Separation: Pneumatic separation influenced by different airflow direction can be achieved by changing the arrangement of high-pressure value. The pneumatic separation test system mainly consists of conveyor belt, queuing system, machine vision system, control system, and high-pressure air injection system. This system cleans and classifies products in a wide range of sizes and weights, separating them into two groups with a uniform column of air. It is used for precise finish sorting, high volume scalping or pre-cleaning operations.

4- Separation by density (in water environment): Other way to separate different materials after granulating the material is to try separation by density. Usually, each material has different properties and behave in different way to a water environment. Frequently, heavy materials use to go to the bottom of the tank meanwhile light ones stay in the surface. This method is very useful to a first overview and to analyze and get results in a short space of time.

5- Metal separation: With this method we are able to remove metal contaminants in plastic waste. On one hand, we could use one equipment based just in ferrous materials, which means a magnetic separation and on the other hand, use an equipment able to separate non-ferrous material, as copper to the sample. Usually, this sorting is used as a final step to clean as much as possible the stream we want to obtain.

Figure 9- Metal separation process. Ferrous and nonferrous.

2.3. Inventory of additional fibre and plastics cleaning.

Subsequently, we will describe additional fibre and plastics cleaning machinery to determine the new outstanding technology to extend in relation to the former detected. This search will include different sectors, also having cross-sectorial applications and undeveloped technologies for the automotive sector.

One technology interesting to describe is the following separation. It is a combination of two and used in the footwear industry to separate textile material to other ones. The mechanism is an air-cascade separator to first remove the lighter textile fines and other fine leather and foam residues, followed by a vibrating air-table to provide final separation of rubber from foam or leather. However, alternative, novel air separation processes are currently under development, to provide higher purity and yields of certain material sub-sets, e.g. thermoplastic rubber from leather.

Figure 10-Air separation technologies (a) air-cascade separator and (b) vibrating air-table separator.

Stage 1: Textile fines separation.

For the textile fines separation, a custom air-cascade process has been developed. As depicted in Fig. 3a this works in the following way: the granulated footwear material enters the top of the separator and falls down past a number of shelves. At each shelf air is blown into the mixture, creating mini air vortices in which the textile fines are blown free of the larger particles. By the time the granulated

mixture has passed all shelves and leaves the bottom of the separator, the vast majority of all textile fines have been removed leaving a predominately leather/foam and rubber mix.

Stage 2: Rubber separation.

The second stage of separation aims to liberate rubber granulates from the PU and EVA based foams from sports shoes, or for leather-based shoes the rubber from leather. A suitable means to provide this separation is a vibrating air-table. As depicted in Fig. 3b, the air-table uses air and vibration to separate the heavier rubber that moves up the table from the lighter material that stratifies on top and slides down the table. Separation efficiency is highly dependent upon optimisation of various process parameters, which include: the angle of the vibrating deck; the vibration frequency; the air speed; and the surface characteristics of the deck (i.e. ridges and ruffles).

Zig-Zag Air separator.

Other interesting equipment is the zig-zag separator. The starting material is conveyed into the zig-zag-shaped sifter channel through an airtight feed mechanism. Here, lighter materials are separated from heavier ones using a multiple cross-flow sifting process. The air required for this separation process flows from bottom to top through the sifting channel. The lighter particles are swept away with the air current while heavier particles fall toward the bottom against the flow of air and are discharged at the base of the separator.

The light material carried by the air flow exits out the top through the sifter channel and is conveyed via ducts to the cyclone where it is then separated and discharged through a rotary gate valve. In general, zig-zag air separator systems operate in recirculation mode, where a ventilator blows the purified air back into the base of the separator. For very dusty or moist products it is also possible to operate the system in partial recirculation or suction mode. The required air flow is provided by a radial ventilator.

Figure 11- Zig-Zag air separator.

ZIG-ZAG-Separators are suitable for separation sizes between 0.1 and 10 mm. Basic foundations for a separation are differences within the density and/or particle size and/or particle form.

Froth flotation

Froth flotation is a process for selectively separating hydrophobic materials from hydrophilic. This is used in mineral processing, paper recycling and waste-water treatment industries. Historically this was first used in the mining industry, where it was one of the great enabling technologies of the 20th century. It has been described as "the single most important operation used for the recovery and upgrading of sulphide ores". The development of froth flotation has improved the recovery of valuable minerals, such as copper- and lead-bearing minerals. Along with mechanized mining, it has allowed the economic recovery of valuable metals from much lower grade ore than previously. This process is very useful to separate light fractions to the lightest one by the performance of the material due to their properties.

Figure 12- Froth flotation process

Froth flotation is a process that selectively separates materials based upon whether they are water repelling (hydrophobic) or have an affinity for water (hydrophilic). The process of froth flotation is not solely dependent upon the density of the material; it is also dependent upon its hydrophobic nature.

Since plastics are generally hydrophobic materials, froth flotation has successfully been used for the separation of plastic materials. For example, two plastic materials which are buoyant in a specific liquid phase can be separated from one another by the addition of a wetting agent which selectively adsorbs to one of the plastics and not the other. Thus, the wetting agent acts as a flotation depressant by selectively adsorbing to the surface of a specific plastic, thereby rendering it hydrophilic. However, adsorption to the other plastic is far less pronounced. Consequently, the hydrophobic plastic will continue to float while hydrophilic plastic will sink to the bottom as a result of depressed flotation. The floating plastic can then be recovered from the surface of the mixture.

These types of equipment have been selected to prove the samples and find a proper one to develop the work and tests. The criteria to select them were focused on the environmental and economical sustainability. To sum up, the best equipment which gave us a better

result and a positive feedback in terms of time and efficiency of results was the Zig-Zag separator. That was the main reason to select it and buy it to develop all the analysis for the samples received.

In the following section, we will describe the methodology used and the obtained results.

2.4. Pilot testing of additional cleaning steps at machine manufacturers and recycling companies.

This action will illustrate the different tests and analysis done to evaluate the accuracy, performance and viability of some technologies described above. It will focus on the third stream mentioned in action 2.1. a mix of different materials and with a size less than 3mm.

The reason of selecting a third stream is the homogeneity of the other two streams and they seem easier in treatment. On the contrary, this small fraction had been very difficult to treat. It is composed of different plastics with a way vary characteristics and also it has small pieces of metal and textile. The principal requirements are as follows.

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Current use	Colour
PVC	1.20-1.4	13-8%	Green, blue, yellow.
PP	0.90-0.92	33-28%	Black
PU	0.03-0.05	22-17%	Fawn, beige
HDPE	0.93-0.97	8-3%	Grey, black
ABS	1.06-1.08	17-12%	Grey, black
Textile	1.52 (aprox.)	2%	Black
Rubber	0.95	3%	Grey, black

Table 3 – Material requirements for the 3mm sample.

To know more about this fraction, we have done a diverse number of tests to find the proper technology to treat it and to scale up to the industry facilities.

The previous pre-treatment of ELV plastic, have been done using the recycling pilot plant at AIMPLAS. In these facilities we studied the different components.

Figure 13. AIMPLAS Recycling Pilot Plant and metal separation equipment used (Rapid Vario-FS).

As a first stage, metallic fraction was separated from the rest of the materials. We were able to performance this action using our RAPID VARIO-FS. This equipment works by detecting the metallic parts (ferrous or no-ferrous materials) and rejecting from the rest of the sample.

The major quantity of metallic fraction was composed by small and light filaments of copper. Once this have been done, we were capable to have a separation from the rest of the light materials which compound the sample.

After pre-treatment step, the methodology was to work with three different equipment to compare them and obtain the high quality of the mixed material.

The assessments could be summarized in three actions depending on the methodology used. We tried to separate the samples to Zig-Zag separator, densimetric table and as a final chance, to pelletized in terms to obtain other recovered value.

First results are related to the Zig-Zag separator. We sent some samples to a specialized facility with the objective to separate the different components and evaluate the accuracy. The following results are distributed by the tests done depending on the parameters used in any special case.

Material data:

Plastics/textile/metal mix

Bulk density: 560 g/l

Test	Feeder	Time	Mass heavy material	Mass light material	Feed rate
I	400	23 sec	0,624 kg	0,164 kg	0,12 t/h
II	400	21 sec	0,284 kg	0,374 kg	0,11 t/h
III	400	76 sec	1,904 kg	0,284 kg	0,10 t/h

Table 4- Measure of the three analysis.

The tests were made with different upstream adjustments and the feed rate was approximately 120 kg/h.

At the beginning, having a sample with a small average size and very similar densities it was very difficult to separate one from the others. The difficult work was to find a balance in order to obtain two samples as much different as we are capable in order to have a positive result to the project.

Moreover, we could conclude that by having the sample treated longer, the separation is more effective in terms of division and separation of the heavy and light materials. This result is very interesting to perform a pre-treatment of the material and remove from the whole sample the lighter particles as a diverse type of fibres and textile.

Figure 14- Results of Test III. Light material and heavy material.

Before this test, from AIMPLAS we also try to separate by air density in other equipment but on the contrary of the former one, this air separator had not have the Zig-Zag system, so the effectiveness of the results were not measurable, the final product obtained was very similar to the raw material.

Subsequently, and due to obtain the positive results from the Zig-Zag equipment, we decided to obtain it which means we will have more possibilities to study the behaviour of this stream in a short period of time having the opportunity to increase the knowledge in Ecobulk project by testing and analysing automotive wastes with the objective to reach a proper final product or way to recover them.

Different fractions obtained are not identified yet, nevertheless we also acquire a portable NIR identification to have a quick result of the analysis. Thus, this process is planned as a next step to verify the efficiency of the method and to know clearly what was at the beginning and the results. This final step will be very important to help the Ecobulk consortium.

Parallely, we also sent some samples to be treated by densimetric table, but we don't have feasible results. The pieces of the material are too small to have a viable separation, so we conclude that this kind of equipment is not the appropriate one to this material, at least not in the size range we received the product. It could be possible to try it again but using a higher range of granulometry than 3mm.

Other step forward was pelletizing the material. Firstly, we remove the metallic fraction as explained previously, this metal fraction could be important to reintroduce in another final stream to recover it as a very valuable material. It is composed for copper in a major proportion.

Next, we introduce the material on the machine to agglomerate it (Fig. 6.). This machine works by processing the material using temperature and pressure. Depending on the diameter of the holes, the final result will be a small or bigger product. In this study, the dimension obtained was 3cm large per 0.5cm of diameter.

Figure 15- Pelletizer machine

The analyses were very useful and interesting for the project. Because of the properties of the different materials, we had to pelletize three times to obtain a proper pellet. We will use this structure in both ways, one to feed transformation machines and get a final material product by the compounding technique, which means to mix this mixed material with other polymers or additives in terms to obtain a final product able to manufacture and to place on the market.

On the other hand, it would be interesting also to recover energy by the materials obtained. It could be used to feed industrial processes as cement or concrete industry to recover energy from the heat capacity of the polymers, Polypropylene (44 MJ/kg), Polyethylene (43 MJ/kg) which is very high, nearly to Natural gas (52 MJ/Kg) or Petroleum (42 MJ/kg).

This test is an advanced work for the next point to develop in month 18 to month 21 in which we have to search a high-quality management to concentrate fibres and plastic to transportation. The sequence of the process is exposed at the next pictures.

Figure 16- Pelletizer process to obtain final product.

3. Conclusions

To put it briefly, this deliverable help us to advance in the definition of the end-of-life vehicle final sorting focused in the light fraction.

As we mentioned, light fraction of the shredder vehicle facilities is very difficult to treat, is composed of a different type of materials and all of them have diverse densities, shapes, weight and so on. Nevertheless, we found an equipment optimal to this kind of properties. The zig-zag separator enables us to make a pre-treatment of the samples in terms to separate the lighters from the heaviest ones.

Consequently, the objective is achieved. We obtain almost a high purity textile fibres and plastics fractions by also taking away some contaminants as metallic content and dust. Additionally, we implemented also this technology in our pilot plant in AIMPLAS growing in specialising recycling processes.

On the other hand, a methodology based on densimetric table is unviable for this kind of stream sample received. The small size (3mm) of our sample made very difficult to obtain a proper separation of the different materials.

Also, we could conclude the prior materials around Europe and the most important sectors where are using them. Polyolefins are the preferred materials to manufacture some products as we observed, and the typical segments are packaging, building and construction and automotive. This fits in perfect to the whole project ECOBULK in terms of have a large quantity of raw material to replicate the project in the future.